

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

REPORT ON DATA COLLECTION FRAMEWORK – MATILDE MATRIX

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DELIVERABLE 2.6 - Report on data collection framework - MATILDE matrix

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

COVID	Corona Virus Disease
ESPON	European Spatial Planning Observation Network
IOM	International Organisation of Migration
MIPEX	Migrant Integration Policy Index
NEET	People neither in employment nor in education and training
QL	Qualitative
QN	Quantitative
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner on Refugees

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This report provides the **data collection framework** to assess, from a regional/territorial perspective, the impacts of Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in European rural and mountain areas. The data collection framework, hereinafter **MATILDE Matrix**, provides guidance for the multilevel (EU-aggregate, national, regional and local level) and multidimensional (social, economic, territorial) impact assessment to be conducted in Work package 3 (Social impact assessment of migration), Work package 4 (Economic impact assessment of migration) and Work package 5 (Implementation of MATILDE toolbox in rural and mountain case study regions).

The MATILDE matrix combines migration-specific indicators¹ with indicators on economic growth, employment, access to services, and indicators that consider the urban/rural and mountain linkages and the transformations brought about in rural/mountain regions as a result of migration processes.

The aim of the Matrix is to ensure the **consistency of the analysis** across the following Work Packages and to mitigate the risk of indicators not being available or comparable across countries. It is therefore to be considered the unifying link between the analyses conducted throughout Work package 3 (Social impact assessment of migration), Work package 4 (Economic impact assessment of migration) and Work package 5 (Implementation of MATILDE toolbox in rural and mountain case study regions).

Indicators have been identified by WP leaders in order to collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data for MATILDE dimensions, identified as follows:

- 1) Spatial distribution of TCNs: this dimension is a key starting point to assess the impact of TCNs, as it provides basic background information that allow to quantify and qualify the stocks and trends in TCNs in MATILDE regions.** It is investigated mostly building on data collected for MATILDE Deliverables 2.1, 2.2. and 2.3. It encompasses indicators that provide information regarding: Current spatial patterns of TCNs in and within the region, Current socio-demographic structure of TCNs in and within the region,

¹ Huddlestone et al. 2013

Predominance of nationalities of TCNs in and within the region, New Immigration Destination and Attractiveness of the region for in-migrants and immigrants (= **Indicators SPA**).

- 2) **MATILDE Social Dimensions** (MSDs): social polarization; social cohesion; active participation and citizenship rights; access to and quality of services. These dimensions are examined through the MATILDE social indicators, identified hereinafter as **Indicators SOC**.
- **MATILDE Economic Dimensions** (MEDs): welfare; economic growth; impact on national and regional labour markets; productivity and innovation inside organisations and companies; development of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship; impact of COVID crisis on social entrepreneurship. These dimensions are examined through the MATILDE economic indicators, identified hereinafter as **Indicators ECO**.
- 3) **MATILDE Territorial Dimensions** (MTDs): Urban-rural/mountain interaction; physical transformations of space; sense of belonging to the place; negotiations and conflicts between different groups; visual re-presentations of the territory; creation and re-creation of boundaries; territorial inequalities, environmental transformation, internal and external accessibility. These dimensions are examined through the MATILDE territorial indicators, identified hereinafter as **Indicators TER**.

The **MATILDE matrix is structured as follows**:

- 1) Overview of data sources on different scales, based on the screening conducted in Task 2.1 and 2.2;
- 2) Indicators that will be used for the impact assessment in WP3, WP4 and WP5, and the rationale behind their identification, that is grounded on the preliminary tasks conducted

in the MATILDE project². This section also details the availability of data; comparability across countries and regions; availability of time series; lack of data and possible solutions etc.

3) Limitations and challenges of the set of indicators identified.

Once the data collection is concluded, individual indicators are revised and potentially compiled into composite indicator(s) in order to provide a synthetic overview that summarize complex and multidimensional impacts resulting from migration processes to rural and mountain regions.

² See in particular, Kordel, S. & Membretti, A. (Eds) (2020): *Classification of MATILDE Regions. Spatial Specificities and Third Country Nationals Distribution – MATILDE Deliverable 2.1* and Kordel, S. & Membretti, A. (Eds.) (2020): *Report on Conceptual Frameworks on Migration Processes and Local Development in Rural and Mountain Areas – MATILDE Deliverable 2.4.*

Author: Stefan Kordel

The Horizon 2020 project **MATILDE - Migration ImpAct Assessment To Enhance Integration and Local Development in European Rural and Mountain Regions** - aims to examine the impacts of migration on local development and territorial cohesion, with a specific focus on European rural and mountain regions. The project originates from the understanding that **'place matters'** (Massey 1994; Gieryn 2000; Dreier et al. 2014) and that it is the result of continuous socio-cultural **negotiations**. Such processes of negotiation involve territorial structures and different categories of inhabitants - old and new, temporary and permanent, nationals and foreigners (Membretti & Viazzo 2017). Geographical, structural and socio-territorial aspects influence the impact migration can have on society and the economy. These aspects, in addition, make the difference in terms of the settlement process of migrants and have an impact on the quantitative and qualitative impact of migration processes on those territories.

In order to assess such impacts and processes, MATILDE is carrying out 13 case studies in different regions across Europe. As a preliminary step, the classification of MATILDE regions has been elaborated (see MATILDE Deliverable 2.1) on the basis of their territorial and socio-economic characteristics as well as considering their socio-demographic profiles (absolute numbers and share over total population, age and gender) of TCNs living in MATILDE regions. The classification presented in Deliverable 2.1, has been based on **existing regional typologies** and **socio-economic indicators**.

As a crucial prerequisite for Work Package 3 (Social impact assessment of migration), Work Package 4 (Economic impact assessment of migration), and Work Package 5 (case studies), the data collection framework, elaborated in this report, will set the ground for the assessment of the impact of TCNs on rural and mountain areas. The aim is to select migration, social, economic and territorial indicators in order to develop a comprehensive assessment of TCNs impact, i.e., the interaction between newcomers and local conditions. For this purpose, this report will operationalise the dimensions identified in the proposal, in order to provide a step-wise approach that each country team can deploy to conduct the impact assessment in the regions covered by MATILDE.

The MATILDE dimensions identified in the proposal have undergone further elaboration in the initial phase of the project. The result is a refined set of dimensions that have to be taken into account for the assessment of the impact of TCNs in rural and mountain regions.

Each dimension has been further detailed through the identification of indicators that operationalize the dimensions. Depending upon the specific situation, each country team will adopt the set of indicators detailed in this Matrix to conduct the impact assessment.

To this end, the elements identified in this matrix are:

- Identify or newly formulate **indicators on impact of TCNs arrival and settling in**, considering social, economic and territorial dimensions. Major data providers such as Eurostat, Zaragoza indicators, MIPEX, European Labour Force Survey, OECD database on migrants in OECD regions will be included. Moreover, the spatial distribution of TCNs will be sketched.
- Evaluate **feasibility of data collection**, comparability across countries and regions, availability of time-series and possible lacking data and strategies to deal with.

1. DATABASE

1.1 DATA PROVIDERS QUANTITATIVE DATA

The MATILDE matrix partly builds on the MATILDE database (D2.2) and further includes existing data from secondary sources. Main data providers are

- (1) European Union (EUROSTAT and ESPON) and MATILDE countries
 - Data from national statistical institutes
 - Data from ESPON project (e.g., ESPON PROFECY and ESPON Alps2050)
 - Data from own surveys, e.g.
 - EU SILC (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions)
 - EU LFS (European Labour Force Survey)
 - Eurobarometer
- (2) European Social Survey (ESS-ERIC): e.g. on political participation of immigrants
- (3) GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
 - European Election Studies (EES)
 - European Values Survey (EVS)
 - International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)
- (4) OECD (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development)
 - Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)
 - Database on Migrants in OECD Regions
- (5) National statistical offices
- (6) Statistical offices on regional and local scale
- (7) International organizations such as UNHCR, IOM (e.g., IOM's portal <https://migrationdataportal.org/>)
- (8) Private-run organisations such as GfK (Gesellschaft für Konsumforschung)

1.2 DATA PROVIDERS QUALITATIVE DATA

Besides secondary data, indicators will be created by means of qualitative data to be collected in the course of Work Package 3, 4, and 5.

In order to assess social impact (WP3), qualitative empirical data will be collected in the realms:

- Social polarisation
- Social cohesion
- Active participation
- Access to quality and services

For assessing economic impact (WP4), qualitative interviews aim to understand:

- Welfare
- Impact on national and regional labour markets
- Development of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship
- Impact of COVID crisis on social entrepreneurship

For assessing territorial impact (WP5), qualitative interviews and participatory action research aim to understand:

- Urban-rural/mountain interactions
- Physical transformation of space
- Sense of belonging to the place
- Process of negotiation/conflict between different populations
- Visual re-presentation of the territory
- Creation and re-creation of boundaries
- Territorial inequalities
- Environmental transformation
- Internal and external accessibility

2.1 SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF TCNS

Authors: Stefan Kordel and Tobias Weidinger

DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

In order to assess spatial distribution of TCNs, which allows to quantify and qualify the stocks and trends of TCNs in MATILDE regions, five dimensions will be addressed:

- (1) Current spatial patterns of TCNs in and within the region.** Both quantitative data and qualitative explanations will be considered to assess spatial patterns.
- (2) Current socio-demographic structure of TCNs in and within the region.** Besides quantitative data and statistics, qualitative data will help to better understand the socio-demographic structure of TCNs.
- (3) Predominance of nationalities of TCNs in and within the region.** This dimension encompasses the development of TCNs by citizenship over time.
- (4) New Immigration Destination.** In addition to predominant nationalities, migration history of the respective region will be considered by means of qualitative data.
- (5) Attractiveness of the region for in-migrants and immigrants.** Both quantitative data on migration balance and explanations provided by local stakeholders are included in this dimension.

Table 1. Indicators for the dimensions of spatial distribution

	Dimension	Indicator	QN/ QL	Data provider	Data availability (in years)	Data availability National (NUTS0)	Data availability Sub-national (NUTS2)	Data availability Regional (NUTS3)	Data availability Local (LAU)
SPA 1a	Current spatial patterns of TCNs in and within the region	Number of Third Country Nationals	QN	National statistic institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2018	only available partly ³	only available partly	only available partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Share of Third Country Nationals of Total Population			2018	only available partly	only available partly	only available partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 1b		Number of Third Country Nationals	QL	Interview partners	2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Share of Third Country Nationals of Total			2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

³ “only available party” = data are not available for all MATILDE countries (NUTS0) or regions in MATILDE countries (NUTS2).

		Population							
SPA 2a	Current socio-demographic structure of TCNs in and within the region	Age groups of Third Country Nationals	QN	National statistical institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2018	only available partly	Not available yet	only available partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Share of Female Third Country Nationals of all Third Country Nationals		National statistical institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2018	only available partly	only available partly	only available partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		TOP10 of Third Country Citizenships		National statistical institutes, PLACE database, statistic offices of districts and municipalities	2018	only available partly	only available partly	partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

				, NGOs					
		TOP10 occupations of Third Country Nationals		National statistical institutes, PLACE database, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Educational background of TCNs		National statistical institutes, PLACE database, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2018	only available partly	only available partly	partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 2b		Age groups of Third Country Nationals	QL	Interview partners	2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Share of Female Third							

		Country Nationals of all Third Country Nationals							
		Most important Third Country Citizenships							
		Most important occupations of Third Country Nationals				-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Educational background of Third Country Nationals				-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 3a	Predominance of nationalities of TCNs in and within the region	Development of TOP10 Third Country Citizenships among total TCN	QN	National statistical institutes, PLACE database, statistic offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2008-2018	only available partly	only available partly	partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA		Development	QL	Interview	2020/21	-	-	no, Collection	no, Collection

3b		of most important Third Country Citizenships among total TCNs		partners				by PPs during WP3,4,5	by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 4a	New Immigration Destination	Number of Third Country Nationals	QN	National statistical institutes, statistical offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2013	only available partly	only available partly	partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Increase of TCNs			2013-2018	only available partly	only available partly	partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 4b	New Immigration Destination	Number of Third Country Nationals	QL	Interview partners	2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Increase of TCNs			2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
		Migration history			2020/21	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 5a	Attractiveness of the region for in-migrants	Cumulative total migration balance	QN	National statistical institutes,	2008-2017	only available partly	no	only available partly, Collection by	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

	and immigrants			statistical offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs				PPs during WP3,4,5	
		Cumulative migration balance of foreigners		National statistical institutes, statistical offices of districts and municipalities , NGOs	2008-2017	only available partly	no	only available partly, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SPA 5b		Cumulative total migration balance	QL	Interview persons	2020/2021	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
	Cumulative total migration balance of foreigners								

SPA1a and SPA1b **Dimension “Current spatial patterns of TCNs in and within the region”**

Definition: The indicators in this dimension describe the number and share of TCNs of total population in regions (NUTS3) or certain municipalities (LAU), indicating the current spatial patterns of TCNs in and within the region and providing explanations.

Data availability: Numbers and shares of TCNs on NUTS3 and LAU level (quantitative and qualitative) need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5

Limitations (contentwise): Dimension is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

SPA2a and SPA2b **Dimension “Current socio-demographic structure of TCNs in and within the region”**

Definition: The indicators in this dimension describe proportions of TCNs based on age, gender and nationality as well as occupations and educational background in regions (NUTS3) and municipalities (LAU), indicating the current socio-demographic structure of TCNs in and within the region and providing explanations, e.g. for predominance of particular migrant groups and lacking of others.

Data availability: Data on age groups, gender and TOP10 nationalities as well as occupations and educational background have been collected in WP2 and are provided in MATILDE Database – Deliverable 2.2. On LAU level, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5 for the case study regions.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator does not provide information on the residence status of TCNs.

SPA3a and 4.3b **Dimension “Diversity of nationalities of TCNs in and within the region”**

Definition: The dimension shows changes in the presence of certain nationalities in regions (NUTS3) or municipalities (LAU) based on development of TOP10 TCN citizenships, indicating potential path dependencies and explaining changes.

Data availability: Data on TOP10 nationalities on NUTS3 and LAU level (quantitative and qualitative) need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5

Limitations (contentwise): The dimension does not provide information on the social proximity of TCNs from the same nationality as they may also dissociate themselves from fellow countrymen and -women at the destination. Other commonalities instead may be more important, such as same religion, language or gender. 4.3a holds the danger of methodological nationalism, while 4.3b could provide a more differentiated picture.

SPA4a and SPA4b **Dimension “New Immigration Destination”**

Definition: The dimension shows the variation (increase or decrease) of TCNs (2013-2018) compared to stock of TCNs in 2013, indicating if regions (NUTS3) or certain municipalities (LAU) are established or new destinations for TCNs. Explanations can be given for reasons of change and implications of rapid growth.

Data availability: Data on numbers of TCNs on NUTS3 and LAU level (quantitative and qualitative) need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5

Limitations (contentwise): The dimension only covers a short period of time.

SPA5a and SPA5b **Dimension “Attractiveness of the region for in-migrants and immigrants”**

Definition: The dimension describes positive cumulative migration balance in general and cumulative migration balance of foreigners in specific, indicating the attractiveness of the region (NUTS3) or certain municipalities (LAU) for in-migrants and immigrants.

Data availability: data on cumulative migration balances (of foreigners) on NUTS3 and LAU level (quantitative and qualitative) need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5

Limitations (contentwise): tbd

2.2 SOCIAL IMPACT

Authors: Jussi Laine and Daniel Rauhut

DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

In order to assess social impact, four MATILDE Social Dimensions (MSDs) are addressed:

- (6) social polarisation** we look into income inequality across socio-economic groups or co-existence of different ethnic groups;
- (7) social cohesion** and its constitutive elements will be assessed by analysing social mobility (ability of individuals to change their economic status), social inclusion (possibility of individuals to take part in society) and social capital (cooperation, social bonds and trust among people);
- (8) active participation and citizenship rights** will be analysed in terms of civic and political participation by TCNs, acquisition of equal rights/responsibilities, bridges and links between TCNs and local citizens, social capital;
- (9) access to and quality of services** will be assessed including, but limited to, development of new jobs in the social sectors related to TCNs reception and integration activities, gaps between TCNs and locals in access and fruition of social services, education and trainings, share of NEETs, housing, and use of public transport.

Table 2. Indicators for the MATILDE social dimensions (MSDs)

	Dimension	Indicator	QN/ QL	Data provider	Data availability (in years)	Data availability National (NUTSo)	Data availability Sub-national (NUTS2)	Data availability Regional (NUTS3)	Data availability Local (LAU)
SOC1	Social polarisation / social cohesion	% of TCNs at risk of poverty	QN	Eurostat and national statistical offices	2007-2019	2007-2019	Some missing data	Partly available, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no
SOC2		Spatial segregation of TCNs	QN/ QL	Interviews by PPs	2020-2021			Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SOC3	Social polarisation	Income inequality across socio- economic groups	QL	Interviews by PPs					
SOC4	Access to and quality of services	Overcrowding rate in immigrant households	QN/ QL	Eurostat/ Interviews by PPs	2020-2021	n/a	n/a	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SOC5		Level of psycho-social well-being	QL	Interviews by PPs	2020-2021	n/a	n/a	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SOC6	Social cohesion	Population by educational	QN	Eurostat	2004-2019	2004-2019	Some missing data	n/a	n/a

		attainment level							
SOC7	Active participation and citizenship rights	Number of high-skilled / low skilled workers & TCNs required by sectors	QN/QL	Eurostat and national statistics/ Interviews by PPs	2020-2021			Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SOC8		Young people neither in employment nor in education and training	QN	Eurostat	2004-2019	2004-2019	few data gaps	n/a	n/a
SOC9	Active participation and citizenship rights/ social cohesion	Unemployment rate	QN	Eurostat	2006-2019	Some missing data	n/a	n/a	n/a
SOC10		Immigrant employability	QL	Interviews by PPs	2020-2021			Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
SOC11		Residents who acquired citizenship	QN	Eurostat	2009-2018	No data for Turkey	n/a	n/a	n/a
SOC12		Civic participation/ engagement	QL	Interviews by PPs	2020-2021				

DEFINITIONS, DATA AVAILABILITY AND LIMITATIONS

SOC1 “At risk of poverty”, Dimensions “Social cohesion” and “social polarisation” QN

Definition: The indicator measures low income and poverty, leading to material deprivation and a lifestyle deviating significantly from what the majority population considers a ‘normal’ lifestyle. The poverty rate is the ratio of the number of people whose income falls below the poverty line; taken as half the median household income of the total population.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices

Limitations (contentwise): Low economic status does not automatically prevent social inclusion or cause polarization.

SOC2 “Spatial segregation of TCNs”, Dimensions “Social cohesion” and “social polarisation”

Definition: Refers to the distribution of social groups in space. The causes of spatial segregation encompass sociocultural, institutional, and economic factors.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices, to be collected in the interviews.

Limitations (contentwise): There are diverse forms of segregation with wide-ranging consequences for those subject to it. Impact of integration may be positive or negative. Although the emergence of enclaves may be positive, large segregated zones, tend to lead to negative repercussions for these groups.

SOC3 “Income inequality across socio-economic groups”, Dimension “Social polarisation”

Definition: Income is defined as disposable income in a particular year. It consists of earnings, self-employment and capital income and public cash transfers; income taxes and social security contributions paid by households are deducted. Can be measured by various indicators, such as the Gini coefficient and S90/S10, among others.

Data availability: to be collected in the interviews

SOC4 “Overcrowding rate in immigrant households”, Dimension “Access to and quality of services” QN/QL

Definition: Displays information on the causes of overcrowding in immigrant households. A person is considered as living in an overcrowded household if the household does not have at its disposal a minimum number of rooms equal to: one room for the household; one room per couple in the household; one room for each single person aged 18 or more; one room per pair of single people of the same gender between 12 and 17 years of age; one room for each single person between 12 and 17 years of age and not included in the previous category; one room per pair of children under 12 years of age.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices, to be collected in interviews.

SOC5 “Level of psycho-social well-being”, Dimension “Access to and quality of services”

Definition: Psychological well-being refers to inter- and intraindividual levels of positive functioning that can include one’s relatedness with others and self- referent attitudes that include one’s sense of mastery and personal growth. Subjective well-being reflects dimensions of affect judgments of life satisfaction

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices, to be collected in the interviews

SOC6 “Population by educational attainment level”, Dimension “Social cohesion”

Definition: A standard indicator on formal competence (educational level) in the population by country of origin. Educational attainment refers to the highest level of education that an individual has completed. This is distinct from the level of schooling that an individual is attending.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices

SOC7 “Number of high-skilled / low skilled workers required by sectors”, Dimension “Active participation and citizenship rights”

Definition: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices, to be collected in the interviews

Data availability: Eurostat and national statistic/ to be collected in the interviews

Limitations (contentwise): Difficult to find good statistical data on this problem, but interviews may disclose valuable information on this aspect.

SOC8 “Young people neither in employment nor in education and training”, Dimension “Active participation and citizenship rights”

Definition: The indicator young people neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET) provides information on young people aged 15 to 24 who meet the following two conditions: (a) they are not employed (i.e. unemployed or inactive according to the International Labour Organisation definition) and (b) they have not received any education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. Data are expressed as a percentage of the total population in the same age group, excluding the respondents who have not answered the question ‘participation to education and training’ and in change over 3 years (in % points).

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices, the quarterly EU Labour Force Survey (EU LFS).

Limitations (contentwise): Unemployment by country of origin does not display any information on language skills, competence level, social competence etc. - just if a person is NEET or not.

SOC9 “Unemployment rate”, Dimensions “Active participation” and “social cohesion”

Definition: The unemployment rate is the percent of the labour force that is jobless. It is a lagging indicator, meaning that it generally rises or falls in the wake of changing economic conditions, rather than anticipating them. When the economy is in poor shape and jobs are scarce, the unemployment rate can be expected to rise. When the economy is growing at a healthy rate and jobs are relatively plentiful, it can be expected to fall.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices

Limitations (contentwise): Informal/irregular work is hard to measure. To be filled in by the interviews.

SOC10 “Immigrant employability”, Dimensions “Active participation and citizenship rights” and social cohesion”

Definition: Language skills, formal competence (education), work experience, social competence, networks etc. actually determine a person’s employability. The employment rate also varies by the reason for immigration and background country.

Data availability: to be collected in the interviews

Limitations (contentwise): Should be related to education demands.

SOC11 “Residents who acquired citizenship”, Dimensions “Active participation and citizenship rights” and “social cohesion” QN

Definition: Displays that the immigrant becomes formally a part of the community in the society which s/he lives in and hence becoming a citizen of the country is the result of a successful integration in the host society.

Data availability: Provided by Eurostat and national statistical offices

Limitations (contentwise): Person may be very active in civic life and participation without citizenship. Citizenship does not automatically signify integration.

SOC12 “Civic participation/engagement”, Dimensions “Active participation and citizenship rights” and “social cohesion”

Definition: Civic engagement or civic participation is any individual or group activity addressing issues of public concern. It measures the involvement within a community. The degree to which ones engages relates to how much one can make a difference. Civic engagement includes communities working together in both political and non-political actions. The goal of civic engagement is to address public concerns and promote the quality of the community.

Data availability: to be collected in the interviews

2.3 ECONOMIC IMPACT

Authors: Birgit Aigner-Walder, Simone Baglioni, Maria Luisa Caputo and Rahel Schomaker

For assessing economic impact, firstly, indicators, consisting of both quantitative and qualitative data, are presented that will be processed by qualitative analyses (2.3.1), while, secondly, indicators treated by quantitative analyses are sketched (2.3.2).

2.3.1. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

Table 3. Indicators for the MATILDE economic dimensions (MEDs)

	Dimension	Indicator	QN/ QL	Data provider	Data availability (in years)	Data availability National (NUTS0)	Data availability Sub-national (NUTS2)	Data availability Regional (NUTS3)	Data availability Local (LAU)
ECO1	Impact on national and regional labour markets	Share of migrant workers by activity sectors (education; health; agriculture, forestry, fishery activities; infrastructures for communication, transportation, distribution networks and energy supply systems)	QN	EUROSTAT Labour force surveys, National statistical institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities	2018-2019	partly available (year of the data collection may vary)	Only partly available	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO2	Development of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship	Migrants running or employed by social enterprises and organizations in rural and mountain areas	QL	Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO3		Share of social enterprises and organisations that are mainly aimed at migrants in rural and mountain areas by sector of activity	QN/ QL	National statistical institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities	2020-2021	-	-	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

				Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO4	Impact of COVID crisis on entrepreneurship	Change in the users (migrants/non-migrants) of their existing programs (IT, food banks, health cares, etc.)	QL	Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO5		Change of the activity sectors in order to tackle the new COVID crisis	QL	Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	no, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO6	Impact on national and regional labour markets	Job opportunities by field: - welfare (public health cares; education; interpreters, mediators; etc.) - social enterprises and organizations for projects aiming migrants - Other jobs opportunities that can be related to the migrants' inflow	QL	Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	no, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO7	Welfare	Proportion of people in primary and tertiary	QN	EUROSTAT, National	2014-2020	-	-	only available	only available

		education by migration status or migration background		statistical institutes, Statistic offices of districts and municipalities, NGOs				partly, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	partly, collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO8		Territorial health services activated mainly to respond to specific migrants' needs	QL	Interviews	2020-2021	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
ECO9		Public housing by migration status or migration background of the households	QN	National statistical institutes, Statistic offices of districts and municipalities, NGOs	2015-2019	-	-	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5	no, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

ECO1 “Share of migrant workers by activity sectors”, Dimension “Impact on national and regional labour markets”

Definition: The indicator describes the share of migrant workers by activity sector and by country of birth. Through this indicator we aim to explore the contribution of migrants to the different economic sectors (by activity).

Data availability: At NUTSO Level, the indicator is currently available for the year 2018. Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): The data comparability is limited by the different categorisations of the activity sectors (notably ISIC, International Standard Industrial Classification, or different categories) and by different date of collection.

ECO2 “Migrants running or employed by social enterprises and organisations in rural and mountain areas”, Dimension “Development of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship”

Definition: The indicator describes migrants working at any level in social enterprises and organisations in rural and mountain areas. Through this indicator we aim to explore the contribution of migrants to the social economy.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5 through qualitative interviews by our partners

Limitations (contentwise): We aim to reach a qualitative appreciation of migrants’ involvement in social economy in our regions. We will not be able to provide any quantitative outcome on the number of the migrants working in social enterprises or organisations.

ECO3 “Share of social enterprises and organisations mainly aimed at migrants in rural and mountain areas by activity sector”, Dimension: “Development of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship”

Definition: The indicator describes the share of social enterprises and organisations in rural and mountain areas that are mainly aimed at migrants, by sector of activity. It indicates the part of social enterprises mainly aimed at migrants (by sector of activity) among all the social enterprises and organisations located or operating in rural and mountain areas.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected through interviews during fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): The definition “mainly aimed at migrants” describes a large spectrum of social enterprises and organisations’ aims that may will need to be refined (on the field).

**ECO4 “Change in the users of the existing programs (IT, food banks, health cares, etc.)”,
Dimension “Impact of COVID crisis on social entrepreneurship”**

Definition: The indicator describes the change in the users’ profile (migrants/non-migrants) that are occurred in social enterprises and organisations aimed notably at migrants in COVID era. Through this indicator we aim to appreciate if social enterprises and organisations aimed mainly at migrants have been a source of resilience for the general population during the COVID crisis.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected through interviews during fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): As this indicator is sensitive, social enterprises and organisations may will not wish to share those information (not even as qualitative data).

**ECO5 “Change of the activity sectors in order to tackle the new COVID crisis”, Dimension
“Impact of COVID crisis on social entrepreneurship”**

Definition: The indicator describes the change of the activities of social enterprises and organisations in order to tackle the new COVID crisis. Through this indicator we aim to appreciate if social enterprises and organisations aimed mainly at migrants have been a source of resilience for the general population during the COVID crisis.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected through interviews during fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise):

ECO6 “Job opportunities by field”, Dimension “Impact on national and regional labour markets”

Definition: The indicator describes the creation of new positions in the fields of the welfare and of the services as direct/indirect consequence of the presence of migrants. Through this indicator we aim to appreciate if/how migrants contribute to the creation of new work opportunities in remote and rural areas.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected through interviews during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): To be defined.

ECO7 “Proportion of people in primary/tertiary education by migration status or migration background”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The indicator describes proportion of people in primary/tertiary education by migration status or migration background. Through this indicator we aim to appreciate the proportions of pupils who did migrate in our regions or who have a migration background.

Data availability: At NUTS0 Level, the indicator is currently available for the year 2014 (Eurostat, LFS). Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): This indicator distinguishes only between first-generation immigrants, second-generation immigrants and natives from native background. It does not allow us to distinguish e.g. between EU migrants and TCNs.

ECO8 “Territorial health services activated mainly to respond to specific migrants’ needs”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The indicator describes if/what effect the inflow/outflow of migrants have on territorial health services and if some additional service has been created to respond to specific migrants’ needs. Through this indicator we aim to explore the impact of migrants on the availability/type of health care in remote and rural areas.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected through interviews during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): To be defined.

ECO9 “Public housing accommodation by migration status or migration background of the households”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The indicator describes the share of public housing accommodations inhabited by migrant households. Through this indicator we aim to explore the impact of migrants on public housing in remote and rural areas.

Data availability: Data on NUTS3 and LAU level need to be collected during the fieldwork in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Limitations (contentwise): The description of a ‘migrant’ household or a household with migrant background will vary significantly, e.g. the migration status can be considered using only the Household Reference Person or with very different outcomes considering all the components of the household.

2.3.2. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

Table 4. Indicators for the MATILDE territorial dimensions (MTDs)

	Dimension	Indicator	QN/ QL	Data provider	Data availability (in years)	Data availability National (NUTSo)	Data availability Sub- national (NUTS2)	Data availability Regional (NUTS3)	Data availability Local (LAU)
ECO10a	Welfare	Real gross domestic product (GDP)	QN	Eurostat	2000-2018 (time series)	available	available	available	no
ECO10b		Mean and median income by broad group of citizenship	QN	Eurostat	2003-2019 (time series)	available	no	no	no
ECO10c		Purchasing Power Parities	QN	GfK	2019	available	available	available	2-digit postcodes
ECO10d		General government debt (Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP))	QN	Eurostat	2000-2019 (time series)	available	no	no	no
ECO10e		People at risk of poverty or social exclusion by NUTS2 regions	QN	Eurostat	2003-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	no
ECO11a	Labour Market	Population by educational attainment level, sex, age, country of birth	QN	Eurostat	2004-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	no

ECO11b		Employment rates by sex, age, educational attainment level, country of birth and NUTS 2 regions	QN	Eurostat	1999-2019 (time series)	available	available	available	no
ECO11c		Unemployment rates by sex, age, citizenship and NUTS 2 regions	QN	Eurostat	1999-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	no
ECO12a	Productivity & Innovation	Young people neither in employment nor in education and training by sex, age, citizenship and NUTS 2 regions (NEET rates)	QN	Eurostat	2000-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	no
ECO12b		Early leavers from education and training by sex and country of birth	QN	Eurostat	2004-2019 (time series)	available	no	no	no
ECO12c		Labour productivity per person employed and hour worked (EU27_2020=100)	QN	Eurostat	2005-2019 (time series)	available	no	no	no

ECO12d		Human resources in science and technology and NUTS 2	QN	Eurostat	1999-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	No
ECO13a	Entrepreneurship & Social Entrepreneurship	Employment by age, economic activity and NUTS 2 regions (NACE)	QN	Eurostat	2008-2019 (time series)	available	available	no	no
ECO13b		Business demography and high growth enterprise by NACE and NUTS 3 regions	QN	Eurostat	2008-2017 (time series)	available	available	available	no
ECO13c		Employer business demography by size class and NUTS 3 regions	QN	Eurostat	2008-2017 (time series)	available	available	available	no

ECO10a “Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP)”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: There are two possible definitions of the Gross Domestic Product: (1) Output approach: GDP is the sum of gross value added of the various institutional sectors or the various industries plus taxes and less subsidies on products (which are not allocated to sectors and industries). It is also the balancing item in the total economy production account. (2) GDP is the sum of uses in the total economy generation of income account: compensation of employees plus gross operating surplus and mixed income plus taxes on products less subsidies plus consumption of fixed capital.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

ECO10b “Mean and median income by broad group of citizenship”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The total disposable income of a household is calculated by adding together the personal income received by all of household members plus income received at household level. Missing income information is imputed. Disposable household income includes: (1) all income from work (employee wages and self-employment earnings) (2) private income from investment and property (3) transfers between households (4) all social transfers received in cash including old-age pensions

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not available at a regional level (NUTS2 and NUTS3).

ECO10c “Purchasing Power Parities”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: Purchasing power parities (PPPs) are indicators of price level differences across countries. PPPs tell us how many currency units a given quantity of goods and services costs in different countries. PPPs can thus be used as currency conversion rates to convert expenditures expressed in national currencies into an artificial common currency (the Purchasing Power Standard, PPS), eliminating the effect of price level differences across countries.

Data availability: The Gesellschaft für Konsumforschung (GfK; “Society for Consumer Research” provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator only covers a short period of time.

ECO10d “General government debt”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The government deficit/surplus is the net borrowing/net lending of general government. It is the difference between the revenue and the expenditure of the general government sector. The government debt is defined as the total consolidated gross debt at nominal (face) value at the end of the year in the following categories of government liabilities: currency and deposits, debt securities and loans.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups and there is no information on a regional level (NUTS2 and NUTS3).

ECO10e “People at risk of poverty or social exclusion by NUTS2 regions”, Dimension “Welfare”

Definition: The government deficit/surplus is the net borrowing/net lending of general government. It is the difference between the revenue and the expenditure of the general government sector. The government debt is defined as the total consolidated gross debt at nominal (face) value at the end of the year in the following categories of government liabilities: currency and deposits, debt securities and loans.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

ECO11a “Population by educational attainment level, sex, age, country of birth”, Dimension “Labour Market”

Definition: The educational attainment level of an individual is the highest International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) level successfully completed, the successful completion of an education programme being validated by a recognised qualification, i.e. a

qualification officially recognised by the relevant national education authorities or recognised as equivalent to another qualification of formal education.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): There is no information on the regional level NUTS3 units.

ECO11b “**Employment rates by sex, age, educational attainment level, country of birth and NUTS 2 regions**”, Dimension “**Labour Market**”

Definition: Employment rates are defined as a measure of the extent to which available labour resources (people available to work) are being used. They are calculated as the ratio of the employed to the working age population.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): There is no information on the regional level NUTS3 units.

ECO11c “**Unemployment rates by sex, age, citizenship and NUTS 2 regions**”, Dimension “**Labour Market**”

Definition: The unemployed are people of working age who are without work, are available for work, and have taken specific steps to find work.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): There is no information on the regional level NUTS3 units.

ECO12a “**Young people neither in employment nor in education and training by sex, age, citizenship and NUTS 2 regions (NEET rates)**”, Dimension “**Productivity & Innovation**”

Definition: This indicator provides information on young people who meet the following two conditions: (1) they are not employed and (2) they have not received any education or training in the four weeks preceding

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise):

ECO12b “**Early leavers from education and training by sex and country of birth**”, Dimension “**Productivity & Innovation**”

Definition: This indicator provides information on young people having attained at most lower secondary education and not being involved in further education or training. The numerator of the indicator refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who meet the following two conditions: (1) the highest level of education or training they have completed is ISCED 2011 level 0, 1 or 2 (ISCED 1997: 0, 1, 2 or 3C short) and (2) they have not received any education or training (i.e. neither formal nor non-formal) in the four weeks preceding.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not available at a regional level (NUTS2 and NUTS3).

ECO12c “**Labour productivity per person employed and hour worked (EU27_2020=100)**”, Dimension “**Productivity & Innovation**”

Definition: Labour productivity represents the total volume of output (measured in terms of Gross Domestic Product, GDP) produced per unit of labour (measured in terms of the number of employed persons) during a given time reference period.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups and there is no information on a regional level (NUTS2 and NUTS3).

ECO12d “**Human resources in science and technology and NUTS 2 regions**”, Dimension “**Productivity & Innovation**”

Definition: Human resources in science and technology is defined according to the Canberra Manual as a person fulfilling at least one of the following conditions: (1) successfully completed education at the third level in a science & technology field of study or (2) not formally qualified as above, but employed in a science & technology occupation where the above qualifications are normally required.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

ECO13a “**Employment by age, economic activity and NUTS 2 regions (NACE)**”, Dimension “**Entrepreneurship & Social Entrepreneurship**”

Definition: Employed persons are persons aged 15 years and over who, during the reference week performed work, even for just one hour a week, for pay, profit or family gain or who were not at work but had a job or business from which they were temporarily absent because of something like, illness, holiday, industrial dispute or education and training.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

ECO13b “**Business demography and high growth enterprise by NACE and NUTS 3 regions**”, Dimension “**Entrepreneurship & Social Entrepreneurship**”

Definition: The creation of new enterprises and the closure of unproductive businesses can be seen as an important contributor to business dynamism. In addition to studying the population of active enterprises, the counts and characteristics of enterprise births and deaths are examined. Special attention is paid to High-Growth Enterprises and Gazelles (growth can be measured by the number of employees or by turnover; growth by 10% or more and 10 employees in the beginning of the growth)

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

ECO13c “**Employer business demography by size class and NUTS 3 regions**”, Dimension “**Entrepreneurship & Social Entrepreneurship**”

Definition: The creation of new enterprises and the closure of unproductive businesses can be seen as an important contributor to business dynamism. In addition to studying the population of active enterprises, the counts and characteristics of enterprise births and deaths are examined. Special attention is paid to the impact of these demographic events on employment.

Data availability: The European Statistical Office (Eurostat) provides data for the variable.

Limitations (contentwise): Indicator is not able to differentiate among migrant groups.

2.4 TERRITORIAL IMPACT

Authors: Andrea Membretti, Ingrid Machold and Marzia Bona

DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

	Dimension	Indicator	QN/ QL	Data provider	Data availability (in years)	Data availability National (NUTS0)	Data availability Sub- national (NUTS2)	Data availability Regional (NUTS3)	Data availability Local (LAU)
TER1a	Urban- rural/mountain interactions	Flows of people (TCNs and migration professionals, e.g. Social workers, teachers...)	QN/ QL	National, provincial statistical institute + literature analysis + interviews	2008-18	Yes	Yes	Yes	No, Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER1b		Flows of economic resources (living expenditures of TCNs in rural/mountain areas, resources for reception centres	QN	National, provincial statistical institute + literature analysis	2008-18	No	No	No	Collection by PPs

		and integration programmes)		+ interviews					
TER2	Physical transformation of space	Transformation of the built environment	QN	National statistics institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities, NGOs, interviews	TBD	No	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER3	Sense of belonging to the place	Attachment to the local dimension developed by different communities (foreigners and locals), measured as a score on a specific scale	QL	Interviews, direct observation, local media	TBD	no	no	no	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER4	Process of negotiation/ conflict between different	Observable outcomes of the processes of negotiation/conflict between different	QL	Interviews, analysis of grey material, local media	TBD	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5

	populations	populations insisting on the same territory in terms of public decisions/results							
TER5	Visual re-presentation of the territory	Images of the territory (socio-cultural self/hetero; shared or not representations) produced and circulating inside and outside the local dimension	QL	Interviews, local media, NGOs	TBD	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER6	Creation and re-creation of boundaries	Observable socio-cultural, administrative, physical boundaries produced, changed, removed	QN/ QL	Interviews, direct observation, grey material, literature analysis	TBD	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER7	Territorial inequalities	Inequalities within the territory in terms of distribution of local resources	QN/ QL	National statistics institutes, statistic offices of districts and municipalities, NGOs,	TBD	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5 (also Mentioned in Wp3 and Wp4)

				interviews					
TER8	Environmental transformation	Degree and modalities of recovering of abandoned lands	QN/QL	Interviews with NGOs, Associations	2008-2018	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP3,4,5
TER9a	Internal and external accessibility	Travel time by car to nearest service of general interest (SGI)	QN/QL	ESPON PROFECY and interviews	ESPON PROFECY 2016	no	no	TBD	Collection by PPs during WP 3, 4, 5
TER9b		Travel time by public transport							

DEFINITIONS, DATA AVAILABILITY AND LIMITATIONS

TER1a and TER1b “**Flows of people and of economic resources from the towns to the rural/mountain territories**”, Dimension “**urban-rural/mountain interactions**”

Definition: The indicators describe the flows of people and of economic resources from the towns to the rural/mountain territories linked to TCNs migration processes.

Data availability: NUTS0, NUTS2, NUTS3 and LAU (for local case studies only)

Limitations (contentwise): The sheer number of TCNs will be further disaggregated at LAU level in the case study regions, in order to distinguish among asylum seekers/refugees and TCNs with different permits of staying (distinction to be made based on the reasons based on which the VISA have been issued). Qualitative interviews will allow to go deeper in order to define also the length of staying, motivations and aspirations of TCNs.

TER2 “**Transformation of the built environment**”, Dimension “**Physical transformation of space**”

Definition: Square meters/number of buildings transformed/used due to the arrival of migrants (e.g. reception centres, social housing, public spaces, etc.) at a certain scale (TBD)

Data availability: Local

Limitations (contentwise): Quantitative data will be complemented and interpreted in the light of the information collected through in-depth interviews and focus groups, aiming to gain information on the processes that conducted to the transformation of built environment, the participation of different groups in these processes, their origin (bottom up, top down), and the like.

TER3 “**Attachment to the local dimension developed by different communities**”, Dimension “**Sense of belonging to the place**”

Definition: Attachment to the local dimension developed by different communities (foreigners and locals) and manifested with behaviours or statements

Data availability: Local

Limitations (contentwise): The insights gained from this indicator necessarily reflect only partial view, i.e. cannot assume to represent the different standpoints of local inhabitants. The selection process of interviewees and focus groups participants will aim to include as many different standpoints as possible, also building on MATILDE stakeholder involvement plan (Deliverable 2.8) and on the expertise of local partners whose activities is embedded in the local context.

TER4 “Outcomes of these processes in terms of public decisions/results”, Dimension “Process of negotiation/conflict between different populations”

Definition: Process of negotiation/conflict between different populations (newcomers and old residents) insisting on the same territory, measured as outcomes of these processes in terms of public decisions/results.

Data availability: Local

Limitations (contentwise): The insights gained from this indicator necessarily reflect only partial view, i.e. cannot assume to represent the different standpoints of local inhabitants. Preliminary research conducted by research partners, and the expertise of local partners will contribute taking stock of as many relevant processes as possible.

TER5 “Images of the territory produced and circulating inside and outside the local dimension”, Dimension “Visual re-presentation of the territory”

Definition: Socio-cultural and visual (self/hetero; shared or not) re-presentation of the territory in terms of images produced and circulating inside and outside the local dimension, in relationship to the presence/arrival of migrants.

Data availability: National, Regional, Local

Limitations (contentwise): The insights gained from this indicator necessarily reflect only partial view, i.e. cannot assume to variety of re-presentation of the local context. Preliminary research conducted by research partners, and the expertise of local partners will contribute taking stock of as many representations as possible in order to conduct a meaningful overview.

TER6 “Creation and re-creation of (socio-cultural, administrative, physical) internal/external boundaries in terms of observable outcomes”, Dimension “Creation and re-creation of boundaries”

Definition: Creation and re-creation of (socio-cultural, administrative, physical) internal/external boundaries, produced, changed, removed due (also) to the presence of TCNs and observable at local/extra local levels.

Data availability: Regional, Local.

Limitations (contentwise): The insights gained from this indicator necessarily reflect only partial view, i.e. cannot assume to represent the different standpoints of local inhabitants. Preliminary research conducted by research partners, and the expertise of local partners will contribute taking stock of as many relevant processes as possible.

TER7 “Inequalities within the territory and respect to other bordering areas, Dimension “Territorial inequalities”

Definition: Inequalities within the territory and respect to other bordering areas in relationship to the presence of TCNs

Data availability: Regional, Local.

Limitations (contentwise): tbd

TER8 “Externalities on the environment”, Dimension “Environmental transformation”

Definition: The recovery of abandoned areas is one of the most valuable acts in terms of environmental impact. In some cases, migrants are playing significant role in this direction by activating new projects or enterprises that reactivate the use of land and contribute to the preservation of natural/environmental resources. At the same time, this indicator will consider projects’ activities as part of reception and integration processes for refugees.

Data availability: Regional, Local

Limitations (contentwise): Quantitative data (number and type of projects) will be complemented and interpreted in the light of the information collected through in-depth

interviews and focus groups, aiming to gain information on the processes that conducted to the transformation of built environment, the participation of different groups in these processes, their origin (bottom up, top down), and the like.

TER9a and TER9b **“Travel time by car and by public transport to nearest service of general interest (SGI)”, Dimension “Internal and external accessibility”**

Data availability: ESPON PROFECY has created a dataset to calculate the car distances from basic services. We have already used it in Deliverable 2.1. Since many migrants do not have access to cars, especially at the beginning of their stay, we will fill the gap with interviews.

Limitations (contentwise): The first indicator (TER9a) is calculated as the weighted travel time by car to the closest service. The population of each origin location is used as weighting factor. The travel time by car weighted by the population shows the average travel time that an inhabitant needs to reach the closest service. Thus, this indicator is comparable among services and among different regions, while it cannot illustrate differences between municipalities within a region. We also acknowledge that migrants’ interests and needs may differ from those of the general population, e.g. in terms of specific consumption habits or the need for legal advice. Different priorities in terms of Services of General Interest (SGI) shall therefore be kept in mind. Moreover, the data collected display the distance by private car, which often does not coincide with the life-worlds of TCNs, as they may be most inclined to rely on public transport, especially in the initial phases following their arrival (TER9b).

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